

1 **Axon guidance activation during TNBC resistance**

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8 Netrin receptors suggested to be important for dissemination included UNC5B and UNC5C, and were both
9 activated.

10 Citations

11 1. Lu, X., Le Noble, F., Yuan, L., Jiang, Q., De Lafarge, B., Sugiyama, D., Bréant, C., Claes, F., De
12 Smet, F., Thomas, J.L. and Autiero, M., 2004. The netrin receptor UNC5B mediates guidance events
13 controlling morphogenesis of the vascular system. *Nature*, 432(7014), pp.179-186.

14 2. Boyé, K., Geraldo, L.H., Furtado, J., Pibouin-Fragner, L., Poulet, M., Kim, D., Nelson, B., Xu, Y.,
15 Jacob, L., Maissa, N. and Agalliu, D., 2022. Endothelial Unc5B controls blood-brain barrier integrity.
16 *Nature Communications*, 13(1), p.1169.

17 3. Navankasattusas, S., Whitehead, K.J., Suli, A., Sorensen, L.K., Lim, A.H., Zhao, J., Park, K.W.,
18 Wythe, J.D., Thomas, K.R., Chien, C.B. and Li, D.Y., 2008. The netrin receptor UNC5B promotes
19 angiogenesis in specific vascular beds.

20 4. Purohit, A.A., Li, W., Qu, C., Dwyer, T., Shao, Q., Guan, K.L. and Liu, G., 2012. Down syndrome
21 cell adhesion molecule (DSCAM) associates with uncoordinated-5C (UNC5C) in netrin-1-mediated growth
22 cone collapse. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 287(32), pp.27126-27138.